

Accessory oculomotor nuclei

Group: $F=3.286, p=0.087$
Hemisphere: $F=5.202, p=0.035$
Interaction: $F=1.706, p=0.208$

Ambiguous nucleus

Group: $F=0.662, p=0.426$
Hemisphere: $F=29.633, p<0.0001$
Interaction: $F=0.657, p=0.428$

Accumbens nucleus ##

Amygdalofugal tract

Group: $F=3.351, p=0.084$
Hemisphere: $F=3.345, p=0.084$
Interaction: $F=0.044, p=0.836$

Amygdalohypothalamic tract

Group: $F=0.021$, $p=0.885$
 Hemisphere: $F=9.203$, $p=0.007$
 Interaction: $F=0.034$, $p=0.855$

Anterior amygdala area ##

Amygdaloid taenial area #

Anterior pretectal and subpretectal nuclei

Group: $F=0$, $p=0.999$
 Hemisphere: $F=42.136$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.646$, $p=0.432$

Anterior-commissure

Arcopallium - Amygdalod complex #

Apical hyperpallium

Auditory Field L2

Auditory parts of the nidopallium

Group: $F=1.115$, $p=0.305$
 Hemisphere: $F=3.211$, $p=0.09$
 Interaction: $F=0.041$, $p=0.842$

Basal somatosensory nucleus of the nidopallium

Basal nucleus of Meynert

Bed nucleus of the stria terminalis

Caudal hindbrain

Cerebellar peduncles

Caudocentral septal area

Cerebellar white matter

cochlear-decussation

decussation-of-the-solitary-tract

Corticomesencephalic tract

Diffuse pretecal area #

Dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus

Dorsal paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus #

Dorsal nucleus of the lateral lemniscus

Dorsal part of the periaqueductal gray #

Dorsolateral anterior nucleus of the thalamus

Group: $F=15.961$, $p=0.0008$
 Hemisphere: $F=5.821$, $p=0.027$
 Interaction: $F=2.224$, $p=0.153$

Entopallium

Group: $F=9.804$, $p=0.006$
 Hemisphere: $F=105.449$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.467$, $p=0.503$

Dorsomedial anterior nucleus of the thalamus

Group: $F=7.723$, $p=0.012$
 Hemisphere: $F=20.885$, $p=0.0002$
 Interaction: $F=1.552$, $p=0.229$

Extended amygdala

Group: $F=2.666$, $p=0.12$
 Hemisphere: $F=78.924$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=3.2$, $p=0.091$

Frontoamygdaloid tract

Group: $F=2.924$, $p=0.104$
 Hemisphere: $F=10.265$, $p=0.005$
 Interaction: $F=0.796$, $p=0.384$

Hippocampus

Group: $F=0.596$, $p=0.45$
 Hemisphere: $F=11.495$, $p=0.003$
 Interaction: $F=0.022$, $p=0.885$

Hippocampal-commissure

$t=-0.4819$, $p=0.636$

Hypothalamus

Group: $F=0.37$, $p=0.551$
 Hemisphere: $F=18.959$, $p=0.0004$
 Interaction: $F=0.199$, $p=0.661$

Isthmic nucleus

Isthmolectal tract

Isthmooptic tract

Lateral cerebellum nucleus

Lateral forebrain bundle

Lateral pontine nucleus

Lateral hypothalamus

Lateral preoptic area

Lateral septum #

Lobule 1 of the cerebellum

Lateral striatum

Lobule 10 of the cerebellum

Lobule 2 of the cerebellum

Group: $F=31.278$, $p<0.0001$
 Hemisphere: $F=1.446$, $p=0.245$
 Interaction: $F=0.072$, $p=0.792$

Lobule 4 of the cerebellum

Group: $F=9.953$, $p=0.005$
 Hemisphere: $F=111.734$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.097$, $p=0.759$

Lobule 3 of the cerebellum

Group: $F=16.885$, $p=0.0007$
 Hemisphere: $F=9.831$, $p=0.006$
 Interaction: $F=2.676$, $p=0.119$

Lobule 5 of the cerebellum

Group: $F=4.662$, $p=0.045$
 Hemisphere: $F=10.006$, $p=0.005$
 Interaction: $F=0.303$, $p=0.589$

Lobule 6 of the cerebellum

Lobule 8 of the cerebellum

Lobule 7 of the cerebellum

Lobule 9 of the cerebellum

Mammillary-bodies

Medial forebrain bundle

Medial cerebellum nucleus #

Medial longitudinal fasciculus

Medio ventral part of the periaqueductal gray #

Mesopallium

Mesencephalic reticular formation

Midbrain vocal area

Midbrain

Nigrostriatal tract

Nidopallium

Nucleus of the diagonal band

Oculomotor nerve

Group: $F=0.353$, $p=0.56$
 Hemisphere: $F=4.876$, $p=0.04$
 Interaction: $F=0.661$, $p=0.427$

Olfactory tract

Group: $F=11.837$, $p=0.003$
 Hemisphere: $F=2660.301$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=5.965$, $p=0.025$

Olfactory bulb

Group: $F=0.007$, $p=0.935$
 Hemisphere: $F=160.733$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.176$, $p=0.68$

Olivary cochlear area

Optic tectum

Optic-chiasm

Optic tract

Pallium ##

Preisthmic region of the midbrain

Group: $F=39.647$, $p<0.0001$
 Hemisphere: $F=330.034$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.456$, $p=0.508$

Quintrofrontal tract

Group: $F=2.369$, $p=0.141$
 Hemisphere: $F=2.046$, $p=0.17$
 Interaction: $F=0.128$, $p=0.725$

Preoptic area

Group: $F=4.448$, $p=0.049$
 Hemisphere: $F=0.548$, $p=0.469$
 Interaction: $F=0.845$, $p=0.37$

Rostral hindbrain

Rotundus nucleus

Group: $F=5.622$, $p=0.029$
 Hemisphere: $F=99.775$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=1.8$, $p=0.196$

Septum

Group: $F=2.925$, $p=0.104$
 Hemisphere: $F=15.887$, $p=0.0009$
 Interaction: $F=1.864$, $p=0.189$

Semilunar nucleus

Group: $F=1.203$, $p=0.287$
 Hemisphere: $F=75.792$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.468$, $p=0.503$

Striatopallidal area

Group: $F=3.824$, $p=0.066$
 Hemisphere: $F=49.132$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.811$, $p=0.38$

Striatum

Substantia nigra

Subgenicutate nucleus #

Supraoptic-decussation

Tectal gray #

Tectotegmental decussation #

Tectopretectal tract

Group: $F=16.646$, $p=0.0007$
 Hemisphere: $F=13.985$, $p=0.001$
 Interaction: $F=0.136$, $p=0.717$

Tectotegmental tract (including tectoisthmic tract)

Group: $F=11.538$, $p=0.003$
 Hemisphere: $F=54.351$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.248$, $p=0.624$

Tectothalamic tract

Group: $F=6.976$, $p=0.017$
 Hemisphere: $F=89.953$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=2.042$, $p=0.17$

Unknown rostralateral band

Thalamus

Group: $F=18.788$, $p=0.0004$
 Hemisphere: $F=83.755$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=1.688$, $p=0.21$

Ventral hyperpallium

Group: $F=4.781$, $p=0.042$
 Hemisphere: $F=567.419$, $p<0.0001$
 Interaction: $F=0.271$, $p=0.609$

Ventral tegmental area

Group: $F=0.281$, $p=0.603$
 Hemisphere: $F=20.262$, $p=0.0003$
 Interaction: $F=0.012$, $p=0.913$

vestibular-commissure

$t=0.8353$, $p=0.414$

Ventricle

Total Brain Volume

$t=18$, $p=-0.5631$

